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The Double Calorimetry System in JUNO

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Abstract

The Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory (JUNO) is located in Jiangmen, Guangdong, China, with an overburden of about 700 meters, and its installation is expected to start commissioning in 2024. The primary goal of the JUNO experiment is to determine the neutrino mass hierarchy with a significance of 3 to 4 σ in 6 years of data taking and to precisely measure the mixing parameters. An unprecedented high energy resolution of 3% at 1 MeV is required for this purpose. To achieve this, high optical coverage, the photomultiplier tubes (PMT) with high quantum efficiency, high transparency liquid scintillator (LS), and low backgrounds are needed. An independent double calorimetry system consisting of 17612 20-inch large PMTs (LPMTs) and 25600 3-inch small PMTs (SPMTs) will provide a total photo-coverage of 78% and improving energy resolution, muon reconstruction, supernova neutrino detection. The performances of both types of PMTs reach the requirements. The photomultipliers are all in the process of being installed on the detector. This proceeding will cover the current status of two independent systems, as well as the performance and electronics of both LPMT and SPMT.

1 Introduction

The energy resolution of the detector is important for the neutrino mass hierarchy studies. To improve the photo coverage, a double calorimetry system has been designed in the JUNO experiment. The two calorimetry systems consist of 20-inch PMTs (“Large” PMT, LPMT) and 3-inch PMTs (“Small” PMT, SPMT).

For LPMT, there are 5000 dynode PMTs (R12860-50 HQE, Hamamatsu) and 15000 microchannel plate (MCP) PMTs (GDB-6201, NNVT) [1, 2]. To reduce the risk of implosion reactions, each LPMT is assembled with a 9 mm thick acrylic cover and a 2.3 mm thick stainless steel cover. The waterproof protection is provided with a triple watertight seal, stainless steel shell, ABS and heat-shrinkable tube for enclosure and support. The schematic diagram is shown in Fig 1. For SPMT, 16 PMTs are coupled on one connector. There are 25600 3-inch PMTs (XP72B22, HZC) installed between 20-inch PMTs, as shown in Fig 2 .

Figure 1: The schematic diagram of LPMT system. [1]

Figure 2: The demonstration of the 3-inch PMTs interlaced between the 20-inch PMTs.

2 LPMT system

The analog signal coming from the JUNO 20-inch PMTs is fed to a readout electronics board, the so-called Global Control Unit (GCU) which amplifies the PMT analog signal and converts it to a digital waveform with a 14 bit ADC and a sampling rate of 1 GS/s. Each GCU handles three 20-inch PMTs, in parallel, and it is installed on the CD support structure, very close to the PMTs, inside a water-tight box. The GCU provides the HV to the PMTs. Finally, in order to handle exceptional high rate events, like those coming from a nearby Galactic Supernova burst,, a dedicated 2 GBytes DDR memory has been placed on each GCU readout board to provide a local storage of the events in case of a high input rates [3, 4].

3 SPMT system

The SPMT system is always in photon counting mode between 1 and 10 MeV range. As shown in Figure 3, a SPMT UWB is composed of a front-end board (ABC), two high voltage splitters (HVS) and a GCU. One SPMT UWB can hold 8 receptacles, which means that 128 SPMTs can be connected to one SPMT UWB. There are 8 ASICs on the ABC board for 128 channels and 1 GB of memory. Each HVS contains 8 high voltage units, half of which are for spare units. There are 200 SPMT UWBs on the JUNO detector.

Figure 3: The schematic diagram of SPMT system. [5]

4 Test bench

In the JUNO experiment, many important tests to understand PMT performance have been performed. In order to check if the bare PMT performances comply with the JUNO requirements, all PMTs have been acceptance tested, which include: Photon Detection Efficiency (PDE), Dark Count Rate (DCR), Gain, Peak-to-Valley ratio (P/V), etc.

In the JUNO experiment, we have container system, scanning system and after-pulse system for LPMT. The container system is used to measure PMT performances, it consists of a silicon-iron shielding, which shields from external magnetic fields ($< 5\mu\text{T}$), a Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) unit, 2 stabilized light sources (LED and ps-Laser with 420 nm wavelength), Data taking electronics (CAEN V1742 switched-capacitor digitizer and JUNO electronics), and a DAQ system based on Linux. Scanning system is for the LPMTs' zonal testing and characterization (sub-sample test 5%). There are 7 self-stabilized LEDs, 7 zenith angles, 168 test points for Gain and PDE uniformity, and 24 azimuthal positions (15° steps). The testing room is EMF-free environment. After-pulse System is located inside the darkroom with the geomagnetic shielding. The test bench is shared with the scanning system, but readout is done using CAEN V1751 Digitizer 10bit, 1GS/s [6].

The bare SPMT tests were performed at HZC and the acceptance testing was at Guangxi University. The acceptance testing focused on PMT gain, resolution and dark current rate. The acceptance test bench consists of a high voltage module (CAEN SY5527LC) and the electronics board is a previous version of the final version.

5 Summary

We have performed bare tube testing and acceptance testing for LPMT and SPMT. The Table 1 shows a summary of the LPMT test results. There are 22,400 LPMTs tested, about 9.3% were rejected because they did not meet the specifications required by JUNO. The difference between bare and potted PMTs, such as HV and DCR, the former is due to the change in resistance and the latter one is due to the connections difference [6]. For the SPMTs, a total of 25744 PMTs were tested and unqualified PMTs was about 0.7% and all of them were replaced. Figure 4 shows the preliminary results of SPMT acceptance testing.

The PMTs installation is in progress and the light off commissioning is in progress. The JUNO experiment is expected to start commissioning in 2024.

Table 1: Summary of LPMT test results[6]

Parameters	Bare PMT			PMT with JUNO 1F3 elec.		
	NNVT	HPK	All	NNVT	HPK	All
Number of PMT	15057	5000	20057	1112	732	1844
Gain ($\times 10^7$)	1.03	1.00	1.03	1.00	0.994	0.999
PDE [%] Corrected	30.1	28.5	29.6	27.0	27.7	28.2
DCR [kHz]	49.3	15.3	40.8	32.1	17	26.5
P/V	3.9	3.8	3.9	3.8	3.6	3.7

Figure 4: The preliminary results of SPMT acceptance testing.

References

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